

CHARACTERISTICS OF METABOLISM AND MARKERS OF BIOCHEMICAL DISORDERS IN THE LIVER WITH HEPATITIS

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Abstract. The article presents an analytical overview of modern scientific literature, revealing the peculiarities of the metabolism of the liver in hepatitis and discussed markers of biochemical disorders in various origins and intensity of liver diseases.

Keywords: liver metabolism, markers of biochemical disorders of the liver, hepatitis.

The liver is the most important organ in which biochemical processes take place, which are extremely important for the organism as a whole [11]. It synthesizes proteins (albumin, prothrombin, fibrinogen, other blood coagulation factors), lipids (cholesterol), lipoproteins, bile acids, bilirubin, and bile are formed [2, 15]. The liver utilizes toxic substances that arise in the body and enter the body (antitoxic function) [4, 12]. The liver synthesizes glycogen and, together with the pancreas, participates in the regulation of carbohydrate reserves in the body [14]. Its active role in digestion is that bile emulsifies fats and improves their breakdown by pancreatic lipase [13]. Food breakdown products (fats, fatty acids, glycerol, amino acids, carbohydrates, minerals, water, vitamins) enter the liver through the portal vein, where they are partially deposited, partially processed, used and partially prepared for use by other tissues [10]. In liver diseases, violations of one or another of its functions occur, which is used for diagnostic purposes. The most widely performed in clinical laboratories is the study of violations of pigment, carbohydrate, protein educational functions. In acute inflammatory and toxic lesions of the liver, a significant amount of intracellular enzymes is released from its tissue. Studies of aldolases, alanine and aspartic transaminases (aminoferases), lactate dehydrogenase and its fractions, cholinesterases, and arginases have acquired diagnostic significance [1, 5, 9].

The liver is involved in all stages of fat metabolism. For normal absorption of fat in the intestines, bile is needed. It acts as a detergent and emulsifier of fat, facilitates the work of pancreatic lipase, improves the absorption of fat in the intestine. Phospholipids are synthesized in the liver in the presence of lipotropic substances acting as donors of lipid groups (methionine, choline) or a factor promoting the synthesis of phospholipids (vitamin B12) [5]. With a lack of lipotropic substances, neutral fats accumulate in the liver, and the amount of glycogen decreases. With liver disease, the content of adenosine triphosphate in it decreases, which provides energy for synthetic processes [10, 12].

The level of cholesterol in the blood is the most important indicator of lipid synthesis in the liver. In healthy people, the blood serum contains 3.0-6.5 mmol / l (116-150 mg%) of cholesterol. In hepatitis and cirrhosis of the liver, there is a violation of cholesterol in the blood: hypercholesterolemia, apparently associated with a violation of the excretory function of the liver, less often - hypocholesterolemia associated with a decrease in its synthesis in the liver [3]. The liver also synthesizes very low density lipoproteins and utilizes high density lipoproteins. Chylomicrons and a small proportion of very low density lipoproteins are formed in the epithelial cells of the small intestine. The synthesis and breakdown of lipoproteins proceeds with the participation of lipoprotein lipase, which binds to heparin. It is noted that with cirrhosis of the liver, the content of heparin in the blood decreases. Thus, the liver is involved both in the formation of lipoproteins and in their destruction. In liver diseases (hepatitis, initial forms of liver cirrhosis), dyslipoproteinemia occurs, mainly increased formation of lipoproteins, mainly beta-lipoproteins [8].

The liver carries out the transamination of amino acids, their oxidation to pyruvic acid in the tricarboxylic acid cycle, and protein synthesis. All albumins, 75-90% of alpha globulins, 50% of beta globulins are synthesized in the liver. A healthy liver can produce 13-18 g of albumin daily. Protein synthesis occurs with the participation of energy. One of the reasons for the decrease in the synthetic function of the liver is a decrease in the content of macroergic compounds in it. In severe liver disease, the total amount of whey protein may drop to 40 g/l instead of 80 g/l. The content of albumins is significantly reduced (up to 20 g/l instead of 40 g/l). Under pathological conditions, the liver synthesizes globulins with unusual properties (paraproteins) [6]. In acute inflammatory processes (hepatitis), the level of alpha-globulins increases by 1.5-2 times. Gamma globulins are produced by lymphocytes and cells of the reticuloendothelial system. In chronic hepatitis occurring with severe autoimmune processes, the content of gamma globulins in the blood increases significantly (up to 30%) [4].

In severe violations of liver function, the process of deamination of amino acids is disturbed, which leads to an increase in their content in the blood and urine. If in healthy people the content of amine nitrogen in the blood serum is 50-80 mg/l, then in severe dystrophic processes in the liver it can increase to 300 mg/l (the transfer coefficient of amine nitrogen, expressed in mg% or in mmol/l is 0.7139). It was noted that in acute viral hepatitis, the content of glutathione, glutamic acid, methionine, phenylalanine, serine, threonine in the blood serum increases. In chronic hepatitis, the same changes in the content of amino acids in the blood are found, but they are less pronounced [9]. The liver plays an important role in the metabolism of iron-containing proteins - hemoglobin, myoglobin, cytochromes, etc. [7].

The toxic, insoluble, free bilirubin formed during the catabolism of these proteins, which does not give a direct reaction with the Ehrlich diazo reagent (indirect), is neutralized in the liver by the action of the enzyme bilirubin diglucuronyltransferase by conjugation with glucuronic acids to form bilirubin diglucuronide (Figure 1).

Rice. 1- Scheme of neutralization of bilirubin in the liver

This form of bilirubin is already non-toxic, soluble and direct (giving a direct reaction with a diazo reagent). Further, normally, neutralized bilirubin is actively transferred by the liver to the bile capillaries, enters the intestine and turns into mesobilinogen, part of which is reabsorbed into the blood, enters the liver and undergoes deeper catabolism, and the rest in the intestine turns into the main pigments of feces and urine and is excreted from the body. Most often, biochemical disorders in the liver occur precisely in pigment metabolism. The most important diagnostic and prognostic value is the determination of the content of total bilirubin and its various fractions in the blood serum, the study of urobilin, stercobilin, bile pigments in the urine. These indicators directly or indirectly reflect the process of conversion of bilirubin in the liver. So, with hepatocellular or parenchymal jaundice that develops with acute viral hepatitis, exacerbation of chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis of the liver, alcoholic liver damage, when exposed to a number of toxic substances (chlorinated hydrocarbons, benzene and its derivatives, phosphorus, lead, mercury, arsenic, toxic fungi), as well as some drugs, the capture, conjugation and excretion of bilirubin from liver cells, as well as its regurgitation, are disrupted.

As a result of these violations of the functions of the hepatocyte, there is a moderate or sharp increase in the level of total blood bilirubin (at a rate of not more than $20.1 \mu\text{mol/l}$, from 30 to $60\text{--}85 \mu\text{mol/l}$ in mild form, at $85\text{--}160 \mu\text{mol/l}$ signs appear moderate, above $170 \mu\text{mol/l}$ - severe form) with a predominance of the direct fraction (at a rate of not more than $0\text{--}3.4 \mu\text{mol/l}$), an increase in the level of mesobilinogen (urobilin) in the urine, a decrease in cholesterol levels and an increase in the activity of aminotransferases, as well as dysproteinemia with hypergammaglobulinemia and decreased prothrombin levels [9]. Liver hepatocytes are characterized by a high diversity of enzymatic composition. Liver enzymes, like other organs, are divided into organ-specific and non-specific. For the liver, organ-specific enzymes are ornithine carbamyltransferase, glutamate dehydrogenase, phosphofructaldolase, histidase, sorbitol dehydrogenase. In addition, the fifth isoenzyme of lactate dehydrogenase LDH5 is considered specific [3]. Damage to hepatocytes leads to the release of a significant amount of intracellular enzymes and their accumulation in the blood. In this regard, transaminases, aldolases, and a number of other enzymes have acquired diagnostic significance [5]. Aldolase is a group name for enzymes involved in the mechanisms of aerobic breakdown of carbohydrates. Serum aldolase catalyzes the reverse breakdown of fructose-1,6-diphosphate into two phosphotrioses - phosphoglyceraldehyde and monophosphate dioxyacetone. Serum aldolase activity is elevated in acute epidemic hepatitis

and to a lesser extent in acute toxic hepatitis. In acute viral hepatitis, a 5–20-fold increase in fructose diphosphate aldolase activity is observed in 90% of patients. Its increase occurs 3–15 days before the appearance of other clinical signs of the disease. After 5 days from the onset of the icteric period, the activity of aldolase decreases. An increase in aldolase activity is also noted in anicteric forms of acute hepatitis. In patients with chronic inflammatory processes in the liver, aldolase activity increases slightly, and in a small number of them [10]. Aminotransferases (transaminases) are often used to diagnose inflammatory liver diseases. Aminotransferases in the human body carry out the processes of transamination: the reverse transfer of amino groups of amino acids to keto acids (Figure 2) [11].

Rice. 2- Scheme of transamination of alpha-amino acids with alpha-keto acids, catalyzed by transaminases

The study of the activity of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) has the greatest diagnostic value. These enzymes are widely distributed in various organs and tissues: liver, myocardium, skeletal muscles, kidneys, etc. [8]. In epidemic hepatitis, the activity of aminotransferases increases with great constancy and in the early stages, even before the onset of jaundice. With toxic hepatitis and exacerbation of chronic, the activity of aminotransferases increases by 3–5 times (at a rate of not more than 45 IU / l). Changes in liver cirrhosis are not so regular [16]. Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) is a glycolytic enzyme that reversibly catalyzes the oxidation of 1-lactate to pyruvic acid. LDH requires nicotinamide dinucleotide as an intermediate hydrogen acceptor (Figure 3) [3].

Rice. 3- Chemistry of the lactate dehydrogenase reaction

Five LDH isoenzymes were found in the blood serum. The liver contains LDH5. The enzyme is inhibited by urea, and this property of the enzyme facilitates its determination. In viral hepatitis, the activity of LDH4 and LDH5 is increased in the first 10 days in all patients, the degree of its increase depends on the severity of the disease. The level of activity of total LDH is normal 240–480 IU/l. In acute viral hepatitis, LDH activity in the blood serum is increased in the first days of the icteric period, and in mild and moderate forms of the disease, it quickly returns to normal levels. Severe forms of viral hepatitis, and especially the development of liver failure, are accompanied by a pronounced and longer-term increase in LDH. In obstructive jaundice in the first stages of blockage of the bile ducts, LDH activity is normal, in later stages there is an increase in activity due to secondary liver damage. With liver carcinomas or cancer metastases to the liver, an increase in LDH activity may occur. In

the stage of remission in chronic hepatitis and cirrhosis of the liver, LDH activity in the blood remains within the normal range or slightly increased. With an exacerbation of the process, an increase in the activity of the enzyme is noted [6]. Thus, the analysis of domestic and foreign scientific literature shows the diversity and high diagnostic significance of liver disease markers based on the characteristics of metabolism in hepatocytes and the specifics of biochemical disorders in hepatitis.

LITERATURE.

1. Aprosina 3.G. Chronic active hepatitis as a systemic disease. Moscow: Medicine, 1981. 248 p.
2. Girin V.A. Hepatitis: Modern treatment and prevention. Moscow: Medicine, 2003. 435 p.
3. Grigoriev P.Ya. Clinic and diagnosis of chronic viral hepatitis // Clinical medicine. 1984. V. 62, No. 2. S. 56-61.
4. Enzyme immunoassay in clinical diagnostic laboratories / V.V. Dolgov, N.G. Rakova, V.E. Kolupaev, N.S. Rytikov. Tver: Triada, 2011. 320 p.
5. Dmitiriev G.A., Glazko I.I. Diagnosis of sexually transmitted infections. M.: BINOM, 2007. 320 p.
6. Kazantsev A.P., Matkovsky V.S. Handbook of infectious diseases. 3rd ed., revised. and additional Moscow: Medicine, 2009. 320 p.
7. Komarov F.I., Korovkin B.F., Men'shov V.V. Biochemical studies in the clinic. 2nd ed. L.: Medicine, 1997. 407 p.
8. Korotyaev A.I., Babichev S.A. Medical microbiology, immunology and virology: textbook. for honey. universities. 4th ed. M., 2008. 305 p.
9. Ivlev A.S., Khazanov A.I., Rumyantsev O.N. Prolonged cholestasis in patients with serum immunoglobulin A deficiency // Clinical Medicine. 2007. V. 65, No. 10. S. 131-133.
10. Musil Ya. Fundamentals of biochemistry of pathological processes. M.: Medicine, 1995. 430 p.
11. Biochemistry: textbook. for universities / ed. E.S. Severin. M.: Goetar-Media, 2003. 779 p.
12. Guthik G. Current heratology. Chichester: John Wiley, 2004. 25 p.
13. Prognostic value of serum fibronectin concentration in alconolikcirrhotic patients / S. Neveau, Th. Poynard, A. Abella, J. Rignon // Hematology. 2005. 45 p.
- 14 Schiff L.E.R. Diseases from the liver. 5th ed. Philadelphia: Lirinuott, 2012. 125
15. Tietz N.W. Clinical guide to laboratory tests. Philadelphia: W. B. Saunder Company, 2003. 305
16. Wallhofer H., Schmidt E., Schmidt F.W. Synopsis der Leberkrankheiten. Stuttgart: G. Thime, 2007. 75 p.